

INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL ALISHER NAVOIY

VOLUME 4
ISSUE 1

2024

ALISHER NAVOIY XALQARO JURNALI

4-JILD, 1-SON

МЕЖДУНАРОДНЫЙ ЖУРНАЛ АЛИШЕР НАВОИЙ
ТОМ-4, НОМЕР-1

INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL ALISHER NAVOIY
VOLUME-4, ISSUE-1

TOSHKENT - 2024

ALISHER NAVOIY XALQARO JURNALI

МЕЖДУНАРОДНЫЙ ЖУРНАЛ АЛИШЕР НАВОИЙ | INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL ALISHER NAVOIY

№1 (2024) DOI <http://dx.doi.org/10.26739/2181-1419-2024-1>

BOSH MUHARRIR: | ГЛАВНЫЙ РЕДАКТОР: | CHIEF EDITOR:

MIRZAYEV IBODULLA
f.f.d., professor (O'zbekiston)
МИРЗАЕВ ИБОДУЛЛА
д.ф.н., профессор (Узбекистан)
MIRZAYEV IBODULLA
DSc, professor (Uzbekistan)

BOSH MUHARRIR O'RINBOSARI: | ЗАМЕСТИТЕЛЬ
ГЛАВНОГО РЕДАКТОРА: | DEPUTY CHIEF EDITOR:

JABBOROV NURBOY
f.f.d., professor (O'zbekiston)
ЖАББОРОВ НУРБОЙ
д.ф.н., профессор (Узбекистан)
JABBOROV NURBOY
DSc, professor (Uzbekistan)

TAHRIRIY HAY'ATI:

Muhiddinov Muslihiddin
f.f.d., professor (O'zbekiston)
Sirojiddinov Shuhrat
f.f.d., professor (O'zbekiston)
Rasulov Ravshanxo'ja
f.f.d., professor (O'zbekiston)
Dilorom Salohiy
f.f.d., professor (O'zbekiston)
Sodiqov Qosimjon
f.f.d., professor (O'zbekiston)
Mark Tutan
f.f.d., professor (Fransiya)
Binnatova Almaz Ulvi
f.f.d., professor (Ozarbayjon)
To'xliyev Boqijon
f.f.d., professor (O'zbekiston)
Shodmonov Nafas
f.f.d., professor (O'zbekiston)
Ramiz Asker
f.f.d., professor (Ozarbayjon)
Yo'ldoshev Qozoqboy
f.f.d., professor (O'zbekiston)
Jo'raqulov Uzoq
f.f.d., professor (O'zbekiston)
Funda Toprak
f.f.d., professor (Turkiya)
Nabiulina Guzal
f.f.d., professor (Tatariston)
Yusupova Dilnavoz
f.f.d., dotsent (O'zbekiston)
Rahim Ibrohim
f.f.d., professor (Afg'oniston)
Suvonova Jumagul
f.f.n., dotsent (O'zbekiston)
Asadov Maqsud
f.f.d., dotsent (O'zbekiston)
Sultanov Tulkin
PhD, dotsent (O'zbekiston)
Mirzayev Rahmatilla
y.f.n., dotsent, huquqshunos (O'zbekiston)
Muhitdinova Badia
f.f.n., dotsent (O'zbekiston)
Ruzmanova Roxila
dots., mas'ul kotib (O'zbekiston)
Narziyeva Ma'mura
kotib, o'qituvchi (O'zbekiston)

ILMIY MASLAHAT KENGASHI

Toshqulov Abduqodir
i.f.d., (O'zbekiston)
Xalmuradov Rustam
t.f.d., professor (O'zbekiston)
Eshqobil Shukur
O'zbekiston Respublikasida xizmat
ko'rsatgan madaniyat xodimi, shoir (O'zbekiston)
To'xtasinov Ilhom
p.f.d. (O'zbekiston)
Rixsiyeva Gulchehra
f.f.d., professor (O'zbekiston)
Benedek Peri
f.f.d., professor (Vengriya)
Ko'chiyev Ismat
publisist, O'zbekiston va Belorussiya
yozuvchilar uyushmasi a'zosi (O'zbekiston)
Olimov Karomatillo
f.f.d., professor (O'zbekiston)
Dadaboyev Hamidulla
f.f.d., professor (O'zbekiston)
Aitpayeva Gulnora
f.f.d., professor (O'zbekiston)
Rahmonov Nasimxon
f.f.d., professor (O'zbekiston)
Shomusarov Shorustam
f.f.d., professor (O'zbekiston)
Dyu Rye Andre
f.f.d., professor (Fransiya)
Pervin Chapan
f.f.d., professor (Turkiya)
Hamroyev Juma
f.f.d., professor (O'zbekiston)
Ibrohimov Elchin
f.f.n., professor (Ozarbayjon)
Jo'rayev Shokirjon
F-m.f.d., professor (O'zbekiston)
Hasanov Shavkat
f.f.d., professor (O'zbekiston)
Nurullo Oltoy
f.f.n., (Afg'oniston)
Xalliyeva Gulnoz
f.f.d., professor (O'zbekiston)
Alim Labib
f.f.d., professor (Afg'oniston)
Nodira Afoqova
f.f.d., professor (O'zbekiston)
Aftondil Erkinov
f.f.d., professor (O'zbekiston)

РЕДАКЦИОННАЯ КОЛЛЕГИЯ:

Мухиддинов Муслихиддин
д.ф.н., профессор (Узбекистан)
Сирожиддинов Шухрат
д.ф.н., профессор (Узбекистан)
Расулов Равшанхужа
д.ф.н., профессор (Узбекистан)
Дилором Салохий
д.ф.н., профессор (Узбекистан)
Содиков Косимжон
д.ф.н., профессор (Узбекистан)
Марк Тутан
д.ф.н., профессор (Франция)
Биннатова Алмаз Улви
д.ф.н., профессор (Азербайджан)
Тухлиев Бокижон
д.ф.н., профессор (Узбекистан)
Шодмонов Нафас
д.ф.н., профессор (Узбекистан)
Рамиз Аскер
д.ф.н., профессор (Азербайджан)
Юлдашев Казакбай
д.ф.н., профессор (Узбекистан)
Журакулов Узок
д.ф.н., профессор (Узбекистан)
Фунда Топрак
д.ф.н., профессор (Турция)
Набиуллина Гузаль
д.ф.н., профессор (Татаристан)
Юсупова Дилнавоз
д.ф.н., доцент (Узбекистан)
Рахим Иброхим
д.ф.н., профессор (Афганистан)
Сувонова Жумагул
к.ф.н., доцент (Узбекистан)
Асадов Максуд
д.ф.н., доцент (Узбекистан)
Султанов Тулкин
PhD, доцент (Узбекистан)
Мирзаев Рахматилла
к.ю.н., доцент (Узбекистан)
Мухитдинова Бадиа
к.ф.н., доцент (Узбекистан)
Рузманова Рохила
доц., отв. секретарь (Узбекистан)
Нарзиева Мамура
секретарь, преподаватель (Узбекистан)

НАУЧНО-КОНСУЛЬТАТИВНЫЙ СОВЕТ:

Тошкуллов Абдукодир
к.э.д., (Узбекистан)
Халмуратов Рустам
д.т.н., профессор (Узбекистан)
Эшкобил Шукур
Заслуженный работник культуры
Республики Узбекистан, поэт (Узбекистан)
Тухтасинов Илхам
д.п.н. (Узбекистан)
Рихсиева Гулчехра
д.ф.н., профессор (Узбекистан)
Бенедек Пери
д.ф.н., профессор (Венгрия)
Кочиев Исмаи
Публицист, член Союза писателей
Узбекистана и Беларуси (Узбекистан)
Олимов Кароматилло
д.ф.н., профессор (Узбекистан)
Дадабаев Хамидулла
д.ф.н., профессор (Узбекистан)
Айтпаева Гулнора
д.ф.н., профессор (Узбекистан)
Рахмонов Насимхон
д.ф.н., профессор (Узбекистан)
Шомусаров Шорустам
д.ф.н., профессор (Узбекистан)
Дю Рье Андре
д.ф.н., профессор (Франция)
Первин Чапан
д.ф.н., профессор (Турция)
Хамроев Джума
д.ф.н., профессор (Узбекистан)
Иброхимов Элчин
к.ф.н., профессор (Азербайджан)
Джураев Шокирджон
д.ф.-м. н., профессор (Узбекистан)
Хасанов Шавкат
д.ф.н., профессор (Узбекистан)
Нурулло Олтой
к.ф.н., (Афганистан)
Халлиева Гулноз
д.ф.н., профессор (Узбекистан)
Алим Лабиб
д.ф.н., профессор (Афганистан)
Нодира Афокова
д.ф.н., профессор (Узбекистан)
Афтондил Эркинов
д.ф.н., профессор (Узбекистан)

EDITORIAL BOARD:

- Mukhiddinov Muslikhiddin**
Doc. of philol. scien., prof. (Uzbekistan)
- Sirojiddinov Shukhrat**
Doc. of philol. scien., prof. (Uzbekistan)
- Rasulov Ravshankhuja**
Doc. of philol. scien., prof. (Uzbekistan)
- Dilorom Salokhiy**
Doc. of philol. scien., prof. (Uzbekistan)
- Sodikov Kosimjon**
Doc. of philol. scien., prof. (Uzbekistan)
- Mark Tutan**
Doc. of philol. scien., prof. (France)
- Binnatova Almaz Ulvi**
Doc. of philol. scien., prof. (Azerbaijan)
- Tukhliev Bokijon**
Doc. of philol. scien., prof. (Uzbekistan)
- Shodmonov Nafas**
Doc. of philol. scien., prof. (Uzbekistan)
- Ramiz Asker**
Doc. of philol. scien., prof. (Azerbaijan)
- Yuldoshev Kozokboy**
Doc. of philol. scien., prof. (Uzbekistan)
- Jurakulov Uzok**
Doc. of philol. scien., prof. (Uzbekistan)
- Funda Toprak**
Doc. of philol. scien., prof. (Turkey)
- Nabiulina Guzal**
Doc. of philol. scien., prof. (Tatarstan)
- Yusupova Dilnavoz**
Doc. of philol. scien., assoc. prof. (Uzbekistan)
- Rakhim Ibrokhim**
Doc. of philol. scien., prof. (Afghanistan)
- Suvonova Jumagul**
Cand. of philol. scien., assoc. prof. (Uzbekistan)
- Asadov Makhsud**
Doc. of philol. scien., prof. (Uzbekistan)
- Sultanov Tulkin**
PhD, assoc. prof. (Uzbekistan)
- Mirzayev Rahmatilla**
Cand. of legal scien., assoc. prof. (Uzbekistan)
- Mukhitdinova Badia**
Cand. of philol. scien., assoc. prof. (Uzbekistan)
- Ruzmanova Rokhila**
Assoc. prof., Exec. Sec. (Uzbekistan)
- Narziyeva Ma'mura**
Secretary, teacher (Uzbekistan)

SCIENTIFIC ADVISORY BOARD:

- Toshkulov Abdukodir**
Doc. of econ. scien., (Uzbekistan)
- Khalmuradov Rustam**
Doc. of technic. scien., prof. (Uzbekistan)
- Eshqobil Shukur**
Honored Worker of Culture of the Republic of Uzbekistan, poet (Uzbekistan)
- Tukhtasinov Ilkhom**
Doc. of pedag. scien. (Uzbekistan)
- Rikhsieva Gulchekhra**
Doc. of philol. scien., prof. (Uzbekistan)
- Benedek Peri**
Doc. of philol. scien., prof. (Hungary)
- Kochiyev Ismat**
Publicist, member of the Writers' Union of Uzbekistan and Belarus (Uzbekistan)
- Olimov Karomatullo**
Doc. of philol. scien., prof. (Uzbekistan)
- Dadaboev Khamidulla**
Doc. of philol. scien., prof. (Uzbekistan)
- Aitpaeva Gulnora**
Doc. of philol. scien., prof. (Uzbekistan)
- Rakhmonov Nasimxon**
Doc. of philol. scien., prof. (Uzbekistan)
- Shomusarov Shorustam**
Doc. of philol. scien., prof. (Uzbekistan)
- Dyu Rye Andre**
Doc. of philol. scien., prof. (France)
- Pervin Chapan**
Doc. of philol. scien., prof. (Turkey)
- Khamroev Juma**
Doc. of philol. scien., prof. (Uzbekistan)
- Ibrokhimov Elchin**
Cand. of philol. scien., prof. (Azerbaijan)
- Juraev Shokirjon**
Doc. of phys.-math. scien., prof. (Uzbekistan)
- Khasanov Shavkat**
Doc. of philol. scien., prof. (Uzbekistan)
- Nurullo Oltoy**
Cand. of philol. scien., (Afghanistan)
- Khallieva Gulnoz**
Doc. of philol. scien., prof. (Uzbekistan)
- Alim Labib**
Doc. of philol. scien., prof. (Afghanistan)
- Nodira Afokova**
Doc. of philol. scien., prof. (Uzbekistan)
- Aftondil Erkinov**
Doc. of philol. scien., prof. (Uzbekistan)

Page Maker | Верстка | Саҳифаловчи: Хуршид Мирзахмедов

Контакт редакций журналов. www.tadqiqot.uz
ООО Тадқиқот город Ташкент,
улица Амира Темура пр.1, дом-2.
Web: <http://www.tadqiqot.uz/>; Email: info@tadqiqot.uz
Тел: (+998-94) 404-0000

Editorial staff of the journals of www.tadqiqot.uz
Tadqiqot LLC The city of Tashkent,
Amir Temur Street pr.1, House 2.
Web: <http://www.tadqiqot.uz/>; Email: info@tadqiqot.uz
Phone: (+998-94) 404-0000

AZIZ MUSHTARIY!

O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti Shavkat Miromonovich Mirziyoyevning "Buyuk shoir va mutafakkir Alisher Navoiy tavalludining 580 yilligini keng nishonlash ro'g'risida"gi PQ-4865-son Qarorida "Alisher Navoiy asarlarida teran ifoda topgan milliy va umuminsoniy g'oyalarning jahon tamaddunida tutgan o'rnini hamda o'sib kelayotgan yosh avlodning intellektual salohiyatini oshirish, ular qalbida yuksak axloqiy fazilatlarini tarbiyalashdagi beqiyos ahamiyatini nazarda tutib, shuningdek, ulug' shoir va mutafakkirning adabiy-ilmiy merosini mamlakatimizda va xalqaro miqyosda yanada chuqur tadqiq qilish va keng targ'ib etish..." lozimligi alohida ta'kidlangan.

Bu filologiya ilmi va navoiyshunoslik, xususan, adabiy ta'sir, qiyosiy adabiyotshunoslik, matnshunoslik va tarjima masalalari bilan shug'ullanayotgan tadqiqotchilar zimmasiga jahonning ilg'or texnologiyalari, nazariy g'oyalarga hamohang ilmiy tadqiqotlar yaratish vazifasini yuklaydi. Olimlarimizning ilmiy salohiyati, innovatsion g'oyalarini jahonda targ'ib qilish va qo'llab-quvvatlash maqsadida xalqaro nufuzga ega ushbu jurnal ta'xis etildi.

"Alisher Navoiy" deb nomlangan ushbu jurnalda navoiyshunoslik, Navoiy adabiy merosining umumjahon tamaddunida tutgan o'rni va adabiy ta'sir masalalari bilan shug'ullanayotgan tadqiqotchilarni o'z maqolalari bilan ishtirok etishga taklif qilamiz.

TAHRIRIYAT

УВАЖАЕМЫЙ ЧИТАТЕЛЬ!

В Постановлении №ПП-4865 Президента Республики Узбекистан Шавката Миромоновича Мирзиёева "О широком праздновании 580-летия со дня рождения великого поэта и мыслителя Алишера Навои" особо отмечается "огромное значение произведений Алишера Навои, в которых нашли глубокое отражение национальные и общечеловеческие ценности, в развитии мировой культуры, их роль в повышении интеллектуального потенциала и духовно-нравственном воспитании молодого поколения, а также в целях обеспечения дальнейшего изучения и популяризации литературно-научного наследия великого поэта и мыслителя..."

Это ставит задачи перед филологами, навоиоведами, исследователями литературного влияния, сравнительного литературоведения, текстологии и вопросов перевода создания научных исследований, соответствующих передовым мировым технологиям и теоретическим идеям. В целях пропаганды и продвижения научного потенциала и инновационных идей наших ученых учреждён данный международный журнал.

Приглашаем публиковать свои статьи в нашем журнале "Алишер Навои" отечественных и зарубежных исследователей, занимающихся изучением жизни и творчества литературы Навои, его роли в мировой литературе, проблемами литературного влияния и сравнительной поэтикой.

РЕДАКЦИОННАЯ КОЛЛЕГИИ

DEAR READER!

Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Miromonovich Mirziyoyev "On the celebration of the 580th anniversary of the great poet and thinker Alisher Navoi" No PP-4865 given the invaluable role of cultivating high moral qualities in their hearts, as well as the need to further study and widely promote the literary and scientific heritage of the great poet and thinker in our country and internationally "

This puts the task of researchers in the field of philology and Navoi studies, in particular, literary influence, comparative literature, textual studies and translation, in creating scientific research in harmony with the world's advanced technologies and theoretical ideas. This internationally renowned journal was established to promote and support the scientific potential and innovative ideas of our scientists around the world.

In this magazine, called "Alisher Navoi", we invite researchers who are interested in Navoi studies, the role of Navoi's literary heritage in world civilization and literary influence to participate with their articles.

EDITORIAL

NAVOIY VA ADABIY TA'SIR MASALALARI

1. **Dilorom Salohiy**
NIZOMIY VA NAVOIY DOSTONLARIDA MAJOZIY TASVIR NAMUNASI.....9
2. **Nurboy Jabborov**
TURKIY RUHIYAT – ALISHER NAVOIY IJOD KONSEPSIYASINING ASOSI.....15
3. **Ozoda Tojiboyeva**
ALISHER NAVOIY IJODINING ROSSIYADAGI MANBALARI VA TAVSIFLARI.....23
4. **Sherxon Qorayev**
TEMURIY SHAHZODA MUHAMMAD SULTON VA ALISHER NAVOIY.....30

MA'RIFAT YOG'DUSI

5. **Serpil Soydan**
NEVÂYÎ'NIN FEVÂYIDÜ'L-KIBER DÎVÂNINDA ÂKIBET / HALAS / RAHM / TEMENNA / VEFA REDIFLI GAZELLER ÜZERINE.....36
6. **Martaba Melikova**
ЭСТЕТИЧЕСКИЕ ИДЕАЛЫ В ДУХОВНОМ НАСЛЕДИИ АЛИШЕРА НАВОИ.....44

NAVOIY NASRI VA NAZMI NAFOSATI

7. **Funda Toprak**
BEDÂYÎÜ'L BÎDÂYE'DE MİTOLOJİK UNSURLAR ('ANKÂ-KÂF-SİMÜRĞ VE EJDERHA).....52
8. **Shahlo Rahmonova**
NAVOIY LIRIKASIDA IJTIMOY FAOL AYOL OBRAZI VA POKIZA ISHQ MASALASI.....61
9. **Farida Karimova**
ALISHER NAVOIYNING "BADOYE' UL-BIDOYA" DEVONI DEBOCHASI ALOHIDA ADABIY HODISA SIFATIDA.....71

ILM, OLAM VA OLIM

10. **Elmurod Nasrullayev**
NAVOIYGA DOIR TARIXIY MANBALAR VA ULARNING ILK O'RGANILISHI MASALALARI.....79
11. **Шоира Темирова, Гулбахор Хаджикурбанова, Саодат Юлдашева**
ОСНОВНЫЕ ЭТАПЫ И ДОСТИЖЕНИЯ ТВОРЧЕСТВА АЛИШЕРА НАВОИ.....87

TAQRIZ, TALQIN VA TAHLIL

12. **Ibrohim Haqqul**
SAKINAMEH IS A POEM OF LIFE AND JOY (*Introduction to the book "Sakinameh: history and poetics" by Professor Maksud Asadov*).....92
13. **Ozoda Tojiboyeva**
ELLARNI BIRLASHTIRGAN SHOIR (*Turkiya davlati Bursa shahridagi O'zbek tili va madaniyati markazi ochilishi va "Alisher Navoiy va XXI asr" xalqaro konferensiyasi bo'yicha*).....95

NAVOIY POETIKASI

14. Maysara Eshniyazova

ALISHER NAVOIYNING “SIROJ UL-MUSLIMIN” ASARIDA DINIY-TASAVVUFIY
G‘OYALARNING POETIK IFODASI.....101

NAVOIY VA TILSHUNOSLIK MASALALARI

15. Hamidulla Dadaboyev

“DEVONU LUG‘OTIT TURK”DA IFODALANGAN BOSH VA ICH KIYIM
NOMALARINING HOZIRGI TURKIY TILLARDA VOQELANISHI.....117

16. Ma‘mura Zohidova

O‘ZBEK TILIGA TARJIMA QILINGAN ASARLARDA QO‘LLANGAN AYRIM SO‘ZLAR
IZOHI.....124

NAVOIY VA TA‘LIM-TARBIYA MASALALARI

17. Gulnoza Xoldorova

ALISHER NAVOIY DIDAKTIK QARASHLARINING TURKIY ILDIZLARI.....129

TAQRIZ, TALQIN VA TAHLIL

Ibrohim HAQQUL

Doctor of Philological Sciences.

SAKINAMEH IS A POEM OF LIFE AND JOY

(Introduction to the book “Sakinameh: history and poetics” by Professor Maksud Asadov)

For citation: Ibrohim Haqqul. SAKINAMEH IS A POEM OF LIFE AND JOY (Introduction to the book “Sakinameh: history and poetics” by Professor Maksud Asadov). Alisher Navoi. 2024, vol. 4, issue 1, pp. 92-94

 <http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11508205>

Wine, wine parties, saki (bartenders), and the desire for wine have been the most popular and wonderful themes in Eastern poetry for centuries. They hold a significant position in classic literature, and their scope is so vast that understanding them is crucial to solving problems related to poetry, life, freedom, mortality, and eternity.

Islam significantly impacted the beliefs, lifestyles, and imaginations of the Arabs, replacing some themes with others in literature. Wine became prohibited, leading to a decline in poems about love and wine. However, during the Umayyad era, there was an increase in the writing of poems that invited love and wine. Some of the Umayyad caliphs were so indulged in entertainment and making parties that they drank until dawn.

Passion for wine and goblets was also high in the castles of Iranian kings. It helped to the poets often spoke about wine and entertainment during wine parties and gatherings. Although the negative consequences and illnesses caused by alcohol addiction should not be ignored.

Legend has it that Adam invented grapes, which were a blessing that brought joy and happiness to the world. However, Satan secretly watered the vine with the blood of peacocks, monkeys, lions, and boars. Thus alcohol has been responsible for creating feelings of hatred, enmity, and has even caused bloodshed among people. Some researchers believe that the connection between these animals and grapes is not coincidental. Each animal represented a degree of intoxication, and when people start drinking, they become like proud peacocks.

It is believed that depending on the amount of alcohol consumed, a person can gradually become more intoxicated and eventually lose their mind. In some cases, they may behave like a monkey, or turn into a ferocious lion or even a scary creature like a pig. However, there have been characters in artistic works, such as Soki, Rind, and Ashik, who were known to resist such moral and spiritual distortions. In Eastern poetry, happiness is often seen as a symbol of achieving freedom. It was also important to follow strict rules and guidelines when participating in wine and wine parties. For instance, one book states that: “There were only punctual, intelligent, and eloquent people into

wine parties. Ignorant people were strictly forbidden from participating in such gatherings. It was considered necessary for everyone in the party to be a master of a craft and knowledge someone who does not speak in vain...” Umar Khayyam's saying “if you drink, drink wisely” was more than just a statement.

The notion of wine lover has played an important role in artistic creation, leading to the emergence of a new genre in poetry called Sakinameh. Scholars have taken interest in the development and peculiarities of this genre, resulting in scientific studies by Iranian, Turkish, and Tajik scientists.

Sakinameh is a genre that beautifully describes both external and internal changes in a person. If we consider a glass of heart as the perfect embodiment of love, and the meeting of Irfan and Murshid, which are repeatedly described, then the idea of a person's spiritual state will expand and enrich. Attention is given to the freedom, joy, and leisure of ordinary life in Sakinameh, while also ascribing a romantic and enlightening meaning to events in the external world. Thus, it can be considered the most enjoyable and rewarding form of poetry.

It is often said that the Sakinameh has played a crucial role as a genre in protecting Eastern literature from depression, pessimism, and excessive cynicism. Addressing a benevolent saki to receiving a glass from their hand are a spiritual renewal for rind, ashik and scholars. One of the reasons for this is that they are not aware of how their emotions, moods, and situations will evolve. They experience sadness and a yearning to break free from all kinds of restrictions, which leads to the dream of freedom. This is a testament to the originality and depth of the psychological image portrayed in the Sakinameh.

It is important for young people to bring the spirit of youth, enthusiasm, and passion into science, as it is what drives scientific progress. Therefore, there is a need to encourage the boldness and courage of novice and young researchers. Maksud Asadov, who was born and raised in the Shafirkon district of Bukhara, studied at Bukhara University and pursued post-graduate studies in Tashkent. He chose the Sakinameh genre for his doctoral dissertation, and he proved to achieve more than the expected results in the research of this topic.

The first chapter of his book is dedicated to the emergence and historical development of this genre, as well as the theme of wine in Arabic and Persian-Tajik poetry. Both chapters are filled with facts and information, which indicates his diligence as an author. The poems in the form of Sakinameh are particularly noteworthy in Uzbek literature due to their novelty and interest in observation and interpretation. The young researcher has managed to reveal the symbolism behind wine, which is made from simple grapes, and how it has become a representation of divine grace and joy.

The words such as wine, bar, saki, glass used in sakinameh were also symbolic in nature as mentioned above. In Sufism literature, poets often portrayed a saki as a mentor (murshid), wine (may) as divine love, and a bar (mayxona) as a hotel (xonaqoh). However, not all poets used these terms in the same sense. The author was able to explain the reasons for this without taking a one-sided approach.

According to Turkish scholar A. Karakhani, “Among the famous poets of Turkish literature whose books contain sokinamas, Alisher Navoi is the artist who holds the first place until today....”

Navoi Sakinameh is an early and beautiful example of this genre, written in Uzbek. Despite some opinions about it, there hasn't been a thorough study or analysis. However, Maksud Asadov has successfully completed this demanding work. The author has paid attention to the position of the wine theme in the lyrics of the great poet, as well as the stanzas of the Sakinameh character in “Khamsa” before focusing on Navoi's Sakinameh.

The Sakinameh genre of poetry continued to be popular even after the 15th century. Poets like Muhammadrizo Ogahi, Tabibi, Miri, Avaz Utar, Sultani, Majzub and Nadeem Namangani, in addition to the masnavi form, left a legacy of ghazal-sakinameh, musaddas-sakinameh, rubai-sakinameh, and tarjeband- sakinameh forms, in addition to the masnavi form. It is important that these works are being carefully studied for the first time, revealing new perspectives. Maksud Asadov is a poet and a scientist who recently published a poetry collection. His poems showcase his academic background and his scientific works reflect his poetic side, demonstrating his aptitude for both. If he

continues to pursue knowledge and creativity with unwavering focus, he will undoubtedly achieve greater success. Dear reader! This book, presented to you, can serve as a foundation for this claim.

Iqtiboslar/Сноски/References

1. Asadov M. Sakinameh: history and poetics. – Tashkent: Tafakkur, 2020.

ALISHER NAVOIY XALQARO JURNALI

4-JILD, 1-SON

МЕЖДУНАРОДНЫЙ ЖУРНАЛ АЛИШЕР НАВОИЙ
ТОМ-4, НОМЕР-1

INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL ALISHER NAVOIY
VOLUME-4, ISSUE-1

Editorial staff of the journals of www.tadqiqot.uz
Tadqiqot LLC the city of Tashkent,
Amir Temur Street pr.1, House 2.
Web: <http://www.tadqiqot.uz/>; Email: info@tadqiqot.uz
Phone: (+998-94) 404-0000

Контакт редакций журналов. www.tadqiqot.uz
ООО Тадqiqот город Ташкент,
улица Амира Темура пр.1, дом-2.
Web: <http://www.tadqiqot.uz/>; Email: info@tadqiqot.uz
Тел: (+998-94) 404-0000